

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 15

Noxious *Gymnodinium* species in South African waters

At the height of the 1995-96 summer holiday season, beachgoers and seaside residents in South Africa's largest bay, False Bay (Fig. 1), were overcome by the discomfort of coughing, burning of the nasal passages, difficulty in breathing, stinging eyes and irritation to the skin. Microscopic examination of water samples from the bay, which had turned a dirty olive-green colour, revealed the presence of a species of *Gymnodinium* first recorded in False Bay in 1988. The noxious gases associated with this plankton bloom were initially reported in the Fish Hoek, St. James and Muizenberg areas, but later the effects were also felt at Monwabesi and Koelbaai on the eastern side of False Bay before spreading to the coastal resort of Hermanus in Walker Bay (Fig. 1). These conditions persisted for several weeks. Although the discomforts experienced

were considerable, symptoms were usually relieved on leaving the area, and no long-term effects were noted.

Rapid growth of the human population on and near the margin of False Bay has placed increasing demands on it, both as a prime recreational area, and as a site of disposal of solid and liquid waste. Media interest in this noxious bloom was therefore intense and the event received considerable exposure. Many unsubstantiated reports attributed the bloom either to the increased discharge of sewage into the bay, or to the introduction of the species through ballast water discharge by damaged oil tankers seeking shelter and undergoing repair in the bay.

(Cont'd on p. 2)

Gymnodinium catenatum and autumnal toxicity in Mar del Plata

Outbreaks of paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), some of high intensity, are well known in Argentina. They are normally due to blooms of *Alexandrium catenella* in the fjords of Tierra del Fuego and to *Alexandrium tamarense* on the Atlantic coast. In recent years, both species seem to have expanded their range. The first report of a toxicity outbreak in southern South America was that of Segers (3) who described a mass intoxication with deaths of aborigines following mussel consumption in the Ushuaia in 1886. Curiously, no further outbreak was recorded in this region until 1972, and others have occurred in 1981,

1989, and 1991. The last was unusually intense and persistent, and extended the range of *A. catenella* northwards to 45°15'S in the Pacific and to the Beagle Channel (1, 4).

In the South Atlantic, the first toxic outbreak of *A. tamarense* was detected in 1980 in an area near Peninsula Valdez, and subsequently expanded to almost the entire coastal ecosystem at least be-

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This issue includes a special section on the NATO-SCOR-IOC Advanced Study Institute on the Physiological Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms, Bermuda Biological Station, 27 May-6 June 1996

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Gymnodinium catenatum on west coast of India

Gymnodinium catenatum is a toxic dinoflagellate involved in paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP). It has been reported from western North America, Spain, Australia and Japan. During a study of dinoflagellates and their cysts on the coast of Karnataka, India, we detected both the planktonic (Fig. 1) and cyst forms of *G. catenatum*. This is highly significant in view of earlier reports of PSP in this region. At the time planktonic cells and cysts were located, there was no toxicity in shellfish in the region tested by mouse bioassay. The planktonic cells were present in very low numbers. Whether this accounts for the lack of toxicity is not known. However this finding highlights the need for close monitoring of the coastal waters, sediments and shellfish of Karnataka.

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Fig. 1. Chain of *Gymnodinium catenatum* from coastal waters of Karnataka, India.

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"Noxious *Gymnodinium* species in South African waters"

In 1988, when the *Gymnodinium* species responsible for this event was first recorded in local waters, surfers, swimmers and fisherman suffered eye, nose and throats irritations. The following year a bloom of the same species was responsible for extensive mortalities of mostly sub- and intertidal fauna, including an estimated 40 tons of abalone in the H.F. Verwoerd marine nature reserve (Fig. 1, Horstman et al., 1991).

Despite this species having bloomed on several occasions since it was first observed, never have the noxious effects to humans been so evident as during the 1995-96 event. However, faunal mortalities were small, with the exception of the larval mortalities experienced by several land-based abalone farmers in the Walker Bay area. Furthermore, mussels collected from Muizenberg and tested by mouse bioassay (Delaney, 1985) were found to be toxic, and a warning was issued against the collection of shellfish.

Attempts to identify the *Gymnodinium* species present in False Bay were interesting in that although it possesses some characteristics of several other toxic marine dinoflagellates, it also has features which distinguish it from these species. For example, the presence of aerosol toxins which result in respiratory distress in humans has been associated with *Gymnodinium breve* Davis blooms off the west coast of Florida for many years. The False Bay species is, however, morphologically dissimilar in that it does not possess the apical crest so distinctive of *G. breve*. Instead it bears a greater resemblance to *Gymnodinium mikimotoi* Miyaki et Kominami ex

Fig. 1. False Bay and Walker Bay.

Oda (*G. mikimotoi* is conspecific with *G. nagasakiense* Takayama and Adachi and is a senior synonym for the latter, Takayama and Matsuoka, 1991) common in Japanese waters, and to the north European species *Gyrodinium aureolum* Hulbert. Morphologically the resemblance to *G. mikimotoi* is particularly strong in that the cells are similar in size, are dorso-ventrally flattened, an apical groove is sculpted on the epicone, and girdle displacement and the number and shape of the chloroplasts are essentially identical. The local species, however, differs from *G. mikimotoi* in the shape and position of the nucleus. In *G. mikimotoi* an ellipsoidal and reniform nucleus is longitudinally orientated in the left hand side of the cell, whereas the nucleus of the local species lies horizontally in the hypocone (Fig. 2). Further-

more, although *G. mikimotoi* and *G. aureolum* have been associated with mortalities of marine fauna, the presence of aerosol toxins as encountered in False Bay has apparently not been associated with these species.

The *Gymnodinium* species described here therefore appeared unique until 1993, when New Zealand experienced its first harmful algae bloom problems. Initial indications of toxic alga in New Zealand waters were the mortality of marine organisms on reefs, an outbreak of coughing due to exposure to sea spray aerosols, and the identification of breve-like lipid-soluble toxins in affected shellfish (MacKenzie, 1995). The *Gymnodinium* species responsible was also found to bear a strong resemblance to *G. mikimotoi* but, as with the False Bay species, the nucleus was horizontally

Fig. 2. Light micrographs of the *Gymnodinium* species from False Bay: (a) dorsal view; (b) lateral view; (c) visualization of the nucleus under UV fluorescence after staining with acridine orange, to show its shape and location.

orientated in the hypocone, and not in the left lobe of the cell as in *G. miki-motoi*. This feature according to MacKenzie et al. (in press) is a distinctive and invariable characteristic of the species.

Together these observations indicate the presence of a southern hemisphere *Gymnodinium* species which shares certain features with toxic northern hemisphere *Gymnodinium* species, but has other characteristics which may be sufficient to discriminate it from those species.

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"*Gymnodinium catenatum* and autumnal toxicity in Mar del Plata"

tween San Julian in 49°15'S in Argentina and the coast of Uruguay (2, 5). Since then blooms of *A. tamarensis* have recurred in the Buenos Aires area during spring (6). In this region too in some years, as well as the spring toxicity maximum, there has been a secondary peak in autumn (6), the origin of which has not been established. In autumn 1962, Balech (7) reported the presence in this area, sometimes in abundance, of *Gymnodinium catenatum*, a well known PSP producer, but it was not until 1992 that a toxic outbreak in this region was associated with this species, on the Uruguayan coast of the Plate estuary (5). The repetition of these events in the following years suggests that there may have been earlier outbreaks which were not detected. It is also probable that this species was responsible for PSP at the end of summer 1980 on the Uruguayan coast (8), since it has not yet been demonstrat-

Fig. 1. Distribution and abundance (•: <100 cells l⁻¹; •: 100-300 cells l⁻¹; •: 1500-2400 cells l⁻¹) of *Gymnodinium catenatum* (May 1981) in relation to distribution of salinity (ppt, Fig. 2a) and temperature (°C, Fig. 2b).

ed that the present species, *Alexandrium fraterculus*, is toxic (9). Our study of the annual phytoplankton cycle (1994-95) in the coastal Mar del Plata is in agreement with that of Balech (7), and indicates that *G. catenatum* appears in autumn, which would explain the secondary peak in mussel toxicity in the area. It must be pointed out that the maximum development of *A. tamarensis* is in spring, and it is present in the plankton from late winter to late spring. It is interesting to note that Balech (7) did not observe this species in his study of the annual cycle of this region, which lends support to the idea that it has only recently colonized or been introduced to the area (9).

In the sediments of the Mar del Plata area, resting cysts of *A. tamarensis* are very abundant, and are present throughout the year. The cysts of *G. catenatum* have only been identified once. Thus while blooms of *A. tamarensis* could be initiated *in situ*, the presence of *G. catenatum* seems to be linked to advection of populations from nearby areas, probably from the Plate Estuary. Retrospective analysis of the distribution of *G. catenatum* in a broad area of the shelf

in autumn 1981 indicates that although the main concentrations are associated with the estuarine front of the Plate River (Fig. 1), the distribution is discontinuous and is associated with different water masses. In the coastal region of the Mar del Plata, which seems to be the limit of its distribution, the waters of El Rincon (33.7 ppt, 16.5°C) predominate, while further offshore near the continental slope, *G. catenatum* is associated with subantarctic water (33.7-33.8 ppt, 10-14°C). This discontinuity seems to indicate the existence of more complex phenomena than the simple transport of *G. catenatum* from the Plate Estuary by a stable flow. The plume of the Plate River flows preponderantly to the NNE, but persistent winds from the northerly sector give rise to a countercurrent along the coast (10). This alternation of transport directions could provide a mechanism for inoculating *G. catenatum* into a broad area, where it might subsequently persist and grow only under favourable conditions.

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Awareness of Cyanobacterial or Algal Blooms at the Premonstratensian Monastery of the Green Loch, Soulseat Scotland, from the Twelfth Century, and Cattle Poisonings Attributed to Cyanobacterial Hepatotoxins at this location Eight Hundred Years Later

Are toxic blooms of cyanobacteria and algae becoming more common? This question is one of the most often-received by those who carry out research on toxic blooms and associated poisoning incidents in fresh-, brackish- and marine waters. The question arises from water-users at freshwaters, where drinking supplies and recreational activities are adversely affected by toxic cyanobacterial blooms, and at estuarine and coastal waters where, for example, shellfish harvesting and sales are proscribed if levels of marine algal toxins exceed statutory limits. It has been argued that blooms appear to be more common because researchers are looking more widely and intensively at the problems, that consumers are eating more seafood so cases of illness are more evident, and that statistical data on bloom occurrences are improving (1). In freshwaters, state or national monitoring programmes have shown high occurrences of cyanobacterial blooms with toxicity being detected in at least 50% of the blooms analysed (e.g., 2, 3).

Evidence appears to indicate that freshwater and marine blooms are indeed increasing in distribution, frequency and duration (1, 4, 5). Palaeolimnological analyses of 210Pb-dated sediment cores are making major contributions to the understanding of the history of increasing eutrophication (4, 6). Perhaps of secondary value, but of human interest, are the glimpses of past human awareness of cyanobacterial and algal blooms and scums, and in some cases, of associated poisoning hazards.

A tribal custom among western Queensland Aborigines of Australia of digging soaks for drinking water, rather than taking the water directly from sources thought to contain cyanobacterial scum, indicates a traditional awareness of health hazards presented by such water (7). The written record is perforce fragmentary. Algal and cyanobacterial blooms are not the stuff of great litera-

ture, although there are some exceptions. As suggested by Fogg et al. (8), the comment by Shakespeare's Gratiano in *The Merchant of Venice*, that "There are a sort of men whose visages do cream and mantle like a standing pool" indicates an assumption by the playwright that his audiences would be familiar with blooms and scums. Other indications of the early awareness of these manifestations in Europe are discussed elsewhere (9, 10).

In ongoing research into the toxicity assessment and toxin content of cyanobacterial and algal blooms in UK and other waters (2, 11), this laboratory annually encounters a small number of animal poisonings and human health problems associated with blooms and scums, e.g. (12-14). In late November and early December 1994, at Soulseat Loch, a eutrophic freshwater lake near Stranraer, SW Scotland, six young cattle died, with liver abnormalities, after drinking from the lake which contained a scum-forming bloom of *Oscillatoria*. Two further cattle died in May 1995 at the same waterbody. On the latter occasion it was possible to carry out an integrated investigation of the event with veterinary colleagues (in prep.). In agreement with the signs of hepatotoxicosis in the cattle was the presence of a hepatotoxic bloom and scum of *Oscillatoria agardhii* in the lake and of partially broken down filaments of *O. agardhii* in the animals' rumen contents. Two microcystin hepatotoxins have so far been identified and further work is in progress. The 1994 and 1995 Soulseat Loch cattle deaths are, in sum, attributable to cyanobacterial hepatotoxicosis.

An interview with the farmer who owned the poisoned cattle indicated that Soulseat Loch has a history of annual blooms and scums. Whilst the farmer can attest to this personally for the past 50 years (Mr. D. Little, pers. comm.), evidence suggests that human awareness of blooms and scums at Soulseat

Loch also existed in the twelfth century. The lake is partly bisected by a peninsula, upon which a monastery was founded by Fergus, Lord of Galloway, for monks of the Premonstratensian* order in 1175 A.D. or earlier (15). The monastery became known as the *Monasterium Viridis Stagni* and as the Monastery of the Green Loch, or Stank. Dick (15) suggests that the Latin name is "traceable to the green appearance of the water from time to time by the presence of spore-like vegetable growths". It can be assumed that the monks of the monastery at Soulseat were familiar with cyanobacterial or algal blooms which developed sufficiently to discolour the water and cause offensive odours.

Although cattle deaths at Soulseat eight centuries later are attributed to the ingestion of microcystins in *O. agardhii*, the sceptical may wonder what has been happening in the intervening eight hundred years at this eutrophic site. Surely a few cattle deaths in the 1990's would not have been the only outward signs of toxic blooms over the years? In today's era of "data-sets", we have to acknowledge that those for Soulseat over this period are incomplete. This would have been partly assured by the decline of the *Monasterium Viridis Stagni* as a seat of literacy after the Scottish Reformation of the 1560's, into a ruinous state by 1684.

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* this unnecessarily lengthy name is derived from that of the mother house of this monastic order, Premontre near Laon NE of Paris, founded by St. Norbert at the desire of Calixtus II in 1120. (ed.).

Society News

The members of the international society for the study of harmful algae (provisionally ISSHA), have been sent a call for nominations for officers for the society. The deadline is 1 April 1997 and the vote will be conducted at the 8th International Conference on Harmful Marine Algae, Vigo, Spain, June 1997. Members not attending will be invited to write-in voting on beforehand.

We have also asked for logo design suggestions. Other items to be discussed at Vigo will include the statutes of the Society, its registration, goals, and general structure.

If you are interested in joining the Society and take part in the decisions concerning statutes, goals and structure please use the application form included in Harmful Algae News No. 14 and send it to:

Fax.: (43) 33 13 44 46,
E-mail: hab@bot.ku.dk

Can we predict harmful algae blooms

Studies carried out at the Institute of Marine Sciences in Erdemli, Turkey, since 1994 suggest that *Emiliania huxleyi* blooms are predictable. A long term atmospheric sampling programme of mineral dust on the harbour jetty of the institute has indicated sporadic dust intrusions into the eastern Mediterranean originating from deserts (1). Each pulse of dust is associated with an order of magnitude increase in the atmospheric concentrations of elements like aluminium and iron. These observations are supported by satellite data (NOAA-AVHRR). Corresponding 3-D air-mass back trajectory analyses allow us to model dust uplift and transport with a regional scale atmospheric model which includes dynamical and transport components.

An extraordinary dust storm which originated in the Sahara was observed on 6th April, 1994, and yielded a maximum dust load of 1600 mg m⁻³, the largest ever recorded since the sampling programme started. The Saharan origin of the dust pulse can be seen clearly in AVHRR data for 6 and 7 April 1994. Satellite data from the eastern Mediterranean obtained a week after the event (14-15 April) indicated high reflectance of visible light from the sea surface in regions coinciding with the dust intrusions in the Black Sea, Sea of Marmora, and Mediterranean, suggesting blooms of coccolithophorids. The post-bloom phases of these, when the coccoliths become detached, can increase the reflectance by 25% or more, easily detected by contemporary AVHRR sensors in the visible band (2, 3). This high reflectance can only be observed as the coccoliths are released 7-8 days after a bloom (4) by the present broad spectrum visible channel of AVHRR.

By coincidence, the research vessel of the institute, *R.V. Bilim*, was in the Sea of Marmora at the time the high reflectance patch was seen on the satellite images of 14-15 April 1994, and reported an unusual and very dense red tide. It was so thick that it was almost impossible to observe the wake of the ship. *Noctiluca scintellans* appeared to be the dominant organism, but the presence of *Emiliania huxleyi* could not be established since the samples, which could not be analysed on board, were preserved in formaldehyde which dissolves

carbonate shells. During 1995 it was possible to demonstrate by SEM that the samples collected from the high reflectance region in the Mediterranean contained *E. huxleyi*.

These observations from such diverse environments, from oligotrophic to brackish and from almost pristine to highly polluted, suggest that a common triggering mechanism is involved, and that it was the week old atmospheric dust intrusion. J.H. Martin's hypothesis on iron limitation of phytoplankton productivity has been tested in the equatorial Pacific by fertilizing an area with iron. The result was a doubling of the plant biomass, chlorophyll and production (5). It is important to note that the biologically effective species of iron is Fe II (6). Faust (7) reported that rapid photo-oxidation/reduction reactions of iron species in cloud droplets, with reaction times of the order of minutes, determine the balance of Fe II and Fe III. A balance in favour of Fe (II) is maintained during the daytime, especially when humidity is present together with sunlight. These facts suggest that the formation of photoreduced iron within cloud droplets during daytime and wet dust intrusions lead to the blooms, and that the diel differences in the balance between different forms of iron, combined with the dust transport and humidity patterns of moving storms, lead to the patchy distribution of the blooms.

Having observed the rather unexpected features of dust, Saharan dust transport and its ocean effects in 1994, we planned to detect similar events in 1995. With experimental dust forecasts kindly supplied by the Land-3 project, we had a better chance to detect them. A synoptic scale meteorological event carrying dust was predicted to effect the region on 27-29 March, 1995. Satellite data indicated an area of high reflectance of visible light on 6 April, 1995, near Cyprus. A ferry sailing from Cyprus to Turkey at our request gathered samples from the high reflectance patch, and SEM analyses of the samples confirmed the presence of detached coccoliths. The high reflectance areas appear about a week after the dust events because the formation of detached coccoliths typically requires 6-8 days to develop after the initiation of a bloom.

Thus the photo-reduced iron in the cloud droplets of humid dust intrusions may result in phytoplankton blooms at the sea surface. It is probable that diel variations in the balance between different forms of iron combined with the dust transport and humidity patterns lead to the patchy distribution of blooms, i.e. the patchiness depends on synoptic scale meteorological events. The 1996 dust transport campaign was planned to demonstrate the diurnal characteristics of the iron, and we designed a sampling system which allows us to fix the delicate bioavailable Fe II that may be present in rain samples. In 1996, a dust pulse event was recorded on 8th February by AVHRR in the eastern Mediterranean, and a diurnal cycle of Fe II was demonstrated in rain samples on 8-9 February as predicted. The rapid reoxidation of Fe (II) makes it very reactive, and it should be taken up by the biota immediately. Although it has not been demonstrated at this stage, this nutritional influx is believed to be responsible for the formation of coccolithophores only, or of both these and red tides. This view is based on the simultaneous observation of both *E. huxleyi* and red tide blooms in the Mediterranean and Sea of Marmora during 1994.

It is expected that dust transport and its interactions with water vapour can lead to global effects. The increased cloud albedo due to enhanced production of cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) during coccolithophore blooms could potentially reduce radiation in higher latitudes where clouds are more abundant. On the other hand the suspension of dust in the atmosphere by erosion of desert regions is a function of aridity in these regions, and would decrease with southerly shifts of rain associated with the polar front. Furthermore, coccolithophore blooms release CO₂ and release its absorbion by the ocean, so that atmospheric CO₂ would tend to increase with dust induced blooms. As a result, negative feedback is suggested between atmospheric dust fluxes and global temperatures, leading to cyclic regulation of climate such as occurred during the interglacial periods. It might be argued that iron limitation is not to be expected in land-locked seas like the Mediterranean, and that insoluble complexing of iron with the scarce phosphates is the reason for the oligotrophic nature of these waters. As mentioned, we think that desert dust is a necessary but not sufficient condition, and that the daytime deposition of the dust under cloudy conditions and above some threshold light intensity is required for

the onset of phytoplankton blooms. In fact cyclone tracks over the Mediterranean show that Saharan dust spreads over the eastern Mediterranean during April and May, and the main track then becomes northerly to reach Norway and the North Sea from June to August. This may be the reason for the sporadic increases in DMS and MSA in the North Atlantic from June to August. The growth of *E. huxleyi* through such processes would throw light on climate variability via the formation of DMS, SO₄, and other chemical species and rates of formation of cloud condensation nuclei (9).

Finally, it is suggested that the next iron experiment should not seed the sea water with iron, but inject it directly over clouds with tracers during daytime when solar radiation is above the threshold intensity.

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Identification Service

The IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen, and the Asian Natural Environmental

Science Center offers an identification service. If you have problems with identification of harmful algal species, the Centres may assist you. You should send samples to one of the two addresses given below. It should be noted that this assistance is not given for routine identification/monitoring of samples, but applies to particularly difficult species, or to species that require special techniques e.g. electron microscopy, for identification.

IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, University of Copenhagen, Botanical Institute, Øster Farimagsgade 2D, DK-1353 Copenhagen K., Denmark

Asian Environmental Science Center, The University of Tokyo, Yayoi 1-1-1, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113, Japan.

10 Young Scientist Grants to Attend the VIII International Conference on Harmful Algae (Vigo, Spain, 25-29 June 1997)

The "Federation of European Microbiological Societies" (FEMS) has accepted co-sponsor this conference by supporting (partially) the participation of 10 young scientists.

To qualify for the award of a Young Scientist Grant the applicant must:

- i) be 35 years old or under.
- ii) belong to microbiological society affiliated to FEMS

In the event that the applicant does not belong to a FEMS affiliated society (e.g. a research student), a grant may be awarded on the recommendation of a Sponsor who must be a member of a FEMS society.

Young scientists interested to apply will be sent an application form. Please contact:

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Filamentous and mucilaginous algal blooms in a Corsican Bay (Calvi-France)

In recent decades there have been profound changes in the benthic algal vegetation off the coast near Calvi (Corsica, France). These are probably linked to the disturbing effects of domestic sewage discharge which continually increase along with urbanisation and tourism.

The Oceanographic Research Centre "STARESO" is located in the bay of Calvi and provides an excellent base for carrying out long term studies of algal vegetation. The first part of this study involved mapping the most important seaweeds of the bay (1, 2). The phenology, ecology and epiphytism of *Cystoseira balearica*, the most common furoid in this part of the Mediterranean have been studied (3, 4). Other studies have dealt with microscopic algae (5; epiphytic Cyanophyceae and Bangiophyceae), the influence of pollution on the distribution and ecology of some epiphytic Cyanophyceae (6), and the distribution of the Bangiophyceae in the bay of Revellata (near Calvi Bay). (7, 8, 9).

Other *Cystoseira* species were present in the mediolittoral (*C. compressa* and *C. stricta*) and medium infralittoral zones (*C. spinosa*). Since 1984, the various species of *Cystoseira* and some other algae have shown a clear regression, while certain nitrophilous species (*Cladophora prolifera*, *Halopteris scoparia*, *Colpomenia sinuosa* and *Enteromorpha* sp.) tend to thrive. Furoid algae and especially *Cystoseira* are known to exhibit a marked sensibility to organic wastes and gradually disappear from polluted sites (10). Now other algal associations, including *Halopteris scoparia*, *Dictyota* sp. and *Padina pavonica*, have replaced or interrupted the *Cystoseira* stands in Calvi Bay. In the northern Adriatic, these nitrophilous species are associated with moderately polluted sites (11). In addition, since 1992, we have noted the extensive development of mucilaginous and filamentous aggregates in some parts of the bay. In early spring, large amounts of filaments grow on rocks, macroalgae, gorgonians, and seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*). These new associations are found in all pho-

tophilic zones from 5 to 30 m with some preference for substrates with a southern exposure. The predominant species in these filamentous aggregates is *Nematochryopsis roscoffensis* var. *giganteus* (Chrysophyceae). This species was first described in the bay as *Tribonema marinum* (Xanthophyceae). *Chrysonephos lewisii* is also found in these associations. It is a tropical genus first described in the Mediterranean by Sartoni (12).

In 1995, the first of these filamentous patches appeared near STARESO between 15 and 28 March, 1996. By mid-May, they could be found almost everywhere in Revellata Bay. In some places, their development is very important and affects the growth of the rest of the vegetation by shading the water below and preventing photosynthesis. We have also observed growth of this filamentous association on artificial structures (i.e. metallic structures and ropes). At the "crique de l'égout", some filaments more than 2 m long grow on submerged ropes. On uncovered substrates, a lack of competition with other species and fast growth in these filamentous forms seems to favour the development of new associations. The filamentous species grow preferably as epiphytes on *Dictyota dichotoma* or *Cystoseira balearica* when present, rather than on other macroalgae. *D. dichotoma* appears in various associations in early March. At the "La Bibliothèque", the *Cystoseira balearica* association still exists but is less healthy. During May 1996, the filamentous associations was so prevalent that filaments could be found floating in the water column, free from any substrate. As a result, most of the macroalgae, and some *Posidonia oceanica* leaves are totally shaded and exhibit a markedly reduced growth.

At the end of spring, mucilaginous aggregates also begin to grow in high densities. The first globules were observed on May 29th 1996 at Punta Revellata and in the STARESO area. They mainly contain Chrysophyceae, *Pulvinaria giraudii*. This species can be found on macroalgae and on seagrasses, but is most commonly observed on un-

covered rocks in small streams. Concurrently we noticed patches of blue-green algae and diatoms developing on the macroalgae. The blue-green algae are mostly *Hydrocoleum* sp. and *Pseudanabaena* sp. Due to the lack of competition with other macrophytes, these blue-green algae can develop in the upper infralittoral zone during the summer. Often the layer of blue-green algal filaments trap bubbles of oxygen from photosynthesis and are lifted to the sea surface.

The development of these aggregates is a peculiar phenomenon that changes benthic associations that are of potentially great importance when considering the general ecology of the bay. These changes often involve the occurrence of new and rare algal species, indicative of the need for further taxonomic and ecological studies.

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◆ New Jersey

The first *Aureococcus anophagefferens* brown tide in New Jersey

We report the first known bloom of the "brown tide" picoplankter *Aureococcus anophagefferens*, in New Jersey. In early May, 1995, personnel at Biosphere, Inc., a commercial aquaculture facility in Tuckerton Bay, New Jersey, noted reduced growth of juvenile hard clam, *Mercenaria mercenaria*, in the nursery system. Feeding and development of hard clam larvae were interfered with at all stages; growth cessation was complete by mid-May. Growth recovery of survivors was partial in early July and complete in mid-July.

The observed clam growth reduction coincided with widespread presence of a picoplankton bloom in the general area. Tuckerton Bay comprises the southwestern-most portion of Little Egg Harbor, New Jersey central coast (Fig. 1). Water pumped into hatchery aquaria typically was so turbid that visibility was lowered dramatically. The bloom was prolonged, being most evident from about the first week in May through mid-July. Based on light microscopy, the same phytoplankter apparently persisted, essentially as a monoculture, during this time. Cell counts on June 5, 10 and 15, respectively, were 1.8, 1.5, and $1.1 \times 10^6 \text{ ml}^{-1}$. Effects of the bloom on flora and fauna in the affected bay areas were not determined.

The problem prompted Biosphere, Inc. Biologist G. Zodl to send water samples to the Suffolk County, New York, (Long Island), Department of Health Services (SCDHS). SCDHS has surveyed occurrence of *A. anophagefferens* brown tide since it first appeared in Suffolk County bays in 1985. Brown tide has had severe detrimental effects on flora and fauna in affected Long Island areas, especially the bay scallop, *Argopecten irradians*. Catastrophic brown tide also occurred in Narragansett Bay, Rhode Island in 1985, but not since.

Analysis by SCDHS of June 1995 New Jersey samples by immunofluorescent microscopy (1) revealed cell numbers approaching 10^6 ml^{-1} , well above the minimal levels ($2\text{--}2.5 \times 10^5$) found detrimental to shellfish in laboratory experiments (2) and suggested by field ob-

Fig. 1. Locations in the northeastern United States where *Aureococcus anophagefferens* brown tides have occurred, and of Delaware and Chesapeake Bays where the species has not been detected.

servations (3). Light microscopy picoplankton counts for the same time by G. Zodl approximated the *A. anophagefferens* numbers confirmed by SCDHS. Subsequently, samples were collected in early July from lower Barnegat Bay to Great Bay (just south of Tuckerton Bay), a distance of approximately 20 miles, by New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection (NJDEP) and National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) personnel. Analysis of these by SCDHS, detected *A. anophagefferens* in levels of 2.7 to $4.5 \times 10^5 \text{ cells ml}^{-1}$. Additional interagency cooperative surveys in mid-August, with samples collected by helicopter by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), Region II, spanned the entire New Jersey intercoastal system from the Hudson-Raritan Estuary to Delaware Bay. Counts, again

by SCDHS, indicated that the bloom was in collapse at this time. The organism was found at various sites in Barnegat Bay and to the north, but cell numbers ranged only to a maximum of 2×10^3 . A 1990 survey had found similar *A. anophagefferens* distribution in New Jersey, and had not detected it south of Barnegat Bay, most notably in Delaware or Chesapeake bays (1).

Subsequent to intense ($>10^6 \text{ cells ml}^{-1}$) and widespread catastrophic brown tides in 1985 and 1986 in eastern Long Island, the blooms have recurred annually, with varied level and distribution, e.g. only in Great South Bay in 1994. Incidence in Long Island was more widespread in 1995, when brown tide occurred in south shore and Peconic Bay systems. Although moderate incidence of *A. anophagefferens* in

New Jersey waters has been known since 1987 (4), the major 1995 lower Barnegat Bay *A. anophagefferens* bloom is the only one outside of eastern Long Island since 1985. Chronic summer-long blooms of another picoplankter, *Nannochloris atomus*, responsible for murky, yellowish-brown water in the Barnegat Bay system since at least 1985, may have masked rising abundance of *A. anophagefferens*. The major brown tide in New Jersey in 1995 reaffirms the regional nature of the phenomenon. NJDEP and NMFS, with the assistance of USEPA and SCDHS plan to monitor for brown tide in New Jersey on a regular basis in the future.

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New www site on the microplankton species of the Black Sea, Sea of Marmara Aegean Sea, and Eastern Mediterranean. The web site also includes HAB species and events from the Turkish Seas. I hope you will find my www site interesting. Please visit the www on

<http://bornova.ege.edu.tr:80/~korayt/plankweb/index.html>

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◆ Argentina

Massive mortality of yellow clams, *Mesoderma mactroides*, in Monte Hermosa Beach, Argentina

The yellow clam *Mesoderma mactroides*, an inhabitant of sandy beaches in Buenos Aires province, was an important economic resource for Argentina between 1940 and 1957. Arguing an apparent overexploitation, commercial harvesting was prohibited in 1958, and this legislation has remained in force until the present. In 1995, a study of the population dynamics was begun at the 32 km long Monte Hermosa beach in southern Buenos Aires province, to establish the state of the resource after 37 years of prohibition. During this work, a massive mortality of the species took place between 11 and 17 November. This event resulted in the almost total disappearance of yellow clams from the area. The number of dead animals was estimated in the order of 45 millions, with a mean size of 50 mm, equivalent to about 35 tons total dry weight. Similar mortalities were recorded for this species in Uruguay and southern Brazil in 1994 and 1993-4 respectively, and attributed to phytoplankton blooms (1, 2).

Analyses of the Monte Hermosa samples showed that water parameters were within the normal ranges (3). No traces of heavy metals were found in the clam tissues, nor were diarrhetic, paralytic or haemolytic toxins detected, despite a coincident red tide on the Buenos Aires coast that month (3). Water sam-

ples of November 19 contained mainly centric diatoms, and the dominant species in clam stomachs was *Paralia sulcata*. Strong S-SE winds blew on 10-11 November, with gusts of 40-50 km per hour. Water temperatures varied between 18-19 C. (4).

This is the first record of this phenomenon in Argentina, and although it is possible to discard contamination as the cause, virological and bacteriological studies still need to be made before we can postulate a plausible hypothesis to account for this catastrophe.

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◆ New Zealand

New Zealand update on HABs, 1992-1996

Shellfish biotoxin events in New Zealand have continued to be managed through 1995 and into 1996 by the NZ Marine Biotoxin Management Board. As of July 1st, responsibility for closures passed from the centralized Marine Biotoxin Surveillance Unit to local Health Protection Officers, though central government (MAF Regulatory Authority) will remain responsible for quality assured export products. The flesh testing will continue, and phytoplankton monitoring is included in the management plan. Phytoplankton monitoring continues for shellfish and caged fish, mainly salmon, and mortalities have been avoided. However, wild fish and shellfish were not so lucky during blooms of *Gymnodinium mikimotoi* during 1995 and 1996.

Pseudonitzschia blooms and DA

Blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* were responsible for domoic acid (DA) contamination of scallops in Northland in 1993, and DA was again detected in shellfish in the far north in summer (November to January) 1994-95 and 1995-96. A bloom of predominantly *P. australis* was also detected in March this year in the far south of NZ, at Big Glory Bay, Stewart Island, using whole gene probes provided by Chris Scholin, Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute, USA. *P. multiseriata* was also detected but in negligible numbers. The use of these probes will assist in building up a flora of the genus *Pseudonitzschia* in NZ waters, and has already proved to be a useful monitoring tool.

Pseudonitzschia pungens commonly blooms in the Coromandel and throughout the Marlborough Sounds from spring to autumn, and was responsible for DA in greenshell mussels in Pelorus Sound in December 1994. *P. turgidula* blooms, reaching 6.0×10^6 cells l^{-1} were recorded early to mid-summer 1994, in the Bay of Plenty, causing DA contamination of scallops in that area, and again reached 1.7×10^6 cells l^{-1} in November 1995. Such blooms are not unusual; *Pseudonitzschia* has been recorded in NZ waters for the past 40 years.

Dinophysis blooms and *Prorocentrum* mats

Dinophysis is common throughout NZ waters, and blooms of *D. acuta* (max. $>4.0 \times 10^4$ cells l^{-1} in integrated samples) occurred in Queen Charlotte Sound from late December 1994 to May 1995, and from October 1995 to April 1996. The blooms caused closures to recreational harvesting of blue mussels at West Point in the sound, with okadaic acid (OA) peaking at levels of >95 mg/100g. The closure level is 20mg/100g. A non-toxic strain of *D. acuminata* which commonly occurs with *D. acuta* bloomed in Port Underwood in summer 1994.

Prorocentrum lima has been responsible for OA in oysters at Rangaunu Harbour in the far north. A mat of this alga occurs in channels of the muddy mangrove estuary and when disturbed, e.g., during storms, cells are suspended in the shallow water. This was reflected by the presence of OA in farmed oysters there in May this year.

Raphidophytes in Hauraki Gulf

1992 was a key year for blooms in NZ. At that time raphidophyte dominated blooms spread through Hauraki Gulf, to be followed by a neurotoxic shellfish (NSP) event in January 1993. Raphidophyte blooms have recurred in the gulf every year since, from early spring (August) to summer. Both *Heterosigma akashiwo* and *Fibrocapsa japonica* have caused extensive yellow-brown blooms, accompanied at times by a peppery taste in mussels which temporarily stalled shellfish harvests in the Coromandel. Further south in Timaru Harbour, in January this year, *Heterosigma* reached 66×10^6 cells l^{-1} and divers reported that oily tea-coloured water left a peppery taste in their mouths. That bloom occurred in calm waters with surface temperatures of 18 C, following heavy rainfall.

The 1992-94 raphidophyte blooms occurred during an unusually long-lived El Niño climate pattern. Germination of *Fibrocapsa japonica* cysts in the cool temperatures (>1.0 C lower than the average in 1992) was postulated as a factor

in its dominance. However in 1995 the climate pattern changed, and a weak La Niña pattern produced warmer weather over NZ. The continuing dominance of raphidophytes during the past year could be due to the build up of major cyst beds, particularly in northeastern waters.

... and *Myrionecta*, *Noctiluca* et al

Deep purple blooms of *Myrionecta rubrum* are reported around New Zealand coastline each year. August 1994 saw massive blooms extending >200 km from Northland to the Coromandel, and over large areas in the Marlborough Sounds between October and December, and these were followed in the Gulf by dense brick-red blooms of *Noctiluca scintillans*. *Noctiluca* again bloom in the Coromandel in mid-winter 1995. None of these extensive and long lasting blooms were linked to fish or shellfish mortalities. Pilchards died in Wellington Harbour in December 1993, due to suffocation caused by clogging of the gills with *Tetraselmis* (1.9×10^6 cells l^{-1}). These deaths were not related to the pilchard deaths that occurred around Australia and NZ in 1995, the cause of which is thought to have been a virus infection.

Prorocentrum micans is another common bloom species in NZ, both on the southwest and northeast coasts. January 1994 saw counts of 4.5×10^8 cells l^{-1} in Hawke Bay. The unialgal bloom caused a slimy coating on fish and looked like an oil slick at the surface, with layers seen on echo sounders well below 50 metres.

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◆ Brazil

Liver failure and human deaths at a haemodialysis centre in Brazil: microcystins as a major contributing factor

At a haemodialysis centre in Caruaru, Brazil, 110 (84%) of 131 patients experienced visual disturbances, nausea and vomiting following routine treatment in February 17-20, 1996. On February 20, one patient died with seizure following dialysis. By March 6, twelve patients had died from seizure and/or acute haemorrhage. Subsequently 83 patients developed cholestatic liver disease and of these 32 died from complications of liver failure by mid-April. By August 4, fifty-five patients died, with 44 of these having a common syndrome associated with liver haemorrhage or liver failure.

At the beginning of March, initial reports from medical doctors in the State of Pernambuco implicated hyperchloremia from the chlorinated water supply of the city's Tabocas Reservoir. On reading newspaper articles and watching television reports of the outbreak during late March, Dr. Sandra Azevedo of the University of Rio de Janeiro recognized that the symptoms were not those of chlorine poisoning and suspected that cyanobacterial toxins might be involved. She contacted the State Health authorities with her suspicions and visited Caruaru the same week to collect phytoplankton samples from the reservoir. Phytoplankton counts were not made by the water company at the time of the outbreak but examination of previous year's counts showed that cyanobacteria had dominated the reservoir since 1990, with the most common genera being *Microcystis*, *Anabaena* and *Anabaenopsis*. Dr. Azevedo's samples showed that the most common cyanobacteria present at the end of March were *Aphanizomenon* and two species of *Oscillatoria*. She analyzed the dialysis centre's in-house water treatment system for microcystins by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Chromatograms of methanol extracts from the activated carbon filter demonstrated peaks with the characteristics of microcystins. The largest peak had a retention time corresponding to microcystin-LR, the leucine/arginine variant of these potent cyclic peptide liver toxins, produced by

several genera and species of cyanobacteria. Further examination with sand and anion/cation exchange filters showed microcystin residues in the ppt to ppm range. Samples sent by Dr. Azevedo to Wayne Carmichael's (Ohio) laboratory confirmed these findings using HPLC, enzyme-linked immunosorbant assay (ELISA) and a protein phosphatase inhibition assay (PPIA). Carmichael's laboratory also examined blood sera provided by Brazilian health authorities and the Center for Disease Control in Atlanta, Georgia, from affected patients who were still living and from the liver tissues of deceased patients. The sera and tissues of all patients who had been exposed were positive for microcystins. The ongoing analyses of sera and liver tissue from deceased patients, many of whom were recently exhumed by Brazilian authorities, is providing valuable on dose/effect data that will help establish risk assessment criteria for microcystins in humans. A clinic for survivors set up in Brazil will help monitor their progress and serve as a data base to assess long term health effects including cancer rates, since microcystins are potent liver tumour promoters.

In Carmichael's laboratory, ELISA guided HPLC separation followed by amino acid analysis of microcystins from liver tissues is providing a profile of the microcystins present. In addition, K.L. Reinhart's laboratory (Illinois) is performing mass spectrometric analysis of liver tissues and of isolated microcystins from liver and sera, to provide structural confirmation of the microcystins present. To date, the most common found are microcystins-CR, LR, and possibly WR. Pathological examinations of affected liver tissues by Dr. Victorino Barreto at Pernambuco University showed a uniform pathological picture for the 16 initial victims. The pattern of liver plate disruption was identical with that found in experimental animals exposed to microcystins.

All biological and chemical evidence to date supports the view that microcystins were the major cause of death for

at least 44 of these dialysis patients. One important question is how could lethal levels of microcystins occur in waters receiving standard treatment procedures such as sedimentation, coagulation, filtration, and chlorination. The answer to this question is that the haemodialysis centre did not have water piped directly to it, but had relied on water trucked to the centre and treated in its own sand-filtration carbon-filtration anion/cation exchanger followed by a microfilter. Due to poor removal of chlorine residues, later recognized as due to inadequate maintenance of the in-house water treatment system, it was decided to use untreated reservoir water to avoid chlorine residues in the water used for dialysis. This water contained high levels of microcystins which were not removed by the small inadequately maintained in-house treatment facility of the haemodialysis centre.

There are many important public health lessons and much scientific information to be learned from this first confirmed outbreak of human poisoning involving cyanotoxins. Since most of the world's reservoir and lake based water supplies are subject to increasing nutrient levels, it is highly probable that repeated episodes of cyanotoxin poisoning will occur unless measures are taken to improve our understanding of the role of cyanotoxins in water-borne diseases. These measures should include watershed management to reduce nutrient inputs, cyanotoxin monitoring to alert authorities to the presence of cyanotoxins, and improvements in water treatment techniques to reduce or remove cyanotoxins from water supplies.

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◆ Oman

Early Red Tides

The Sultanate of Oman has not previously been mentioned in this newsletter, and to many readers may appear remote both geographically and from our professional interests. Michael Gallagher of the Natural History Museum in Muscat has prompted me to correct these views. He recently sent me a short note by Thabit Zahran (1), now director of the Marine Science and Fisheries in Muscat, about fish mortalities in Omani waters.

Western knowledge of Oman perhaps begins with the 5th century Greek historian Herodotus who called the coastal inhabitants of the NW Arabian Sea, from Makran to Somalia, *Ichthyophagoi* or fish eaters, an indication of fertile coastal waters. The Arab geographer El Idrisi in a description of the world prepared for the King of Sicily in 1040 A.D. wrote of the coastal tribes there in much the same terms, and so did Lorimer in his *Gazeteer of the Persian Gulf, Oman, and Central Arabia* published in 1915 in Calcutta. These people lived on fish, fed them to their camels, and roofed their dwellings with the skins of whales.

Portuguese commercial motives in the 16th and 17th centuries kindled interest in Oman and two fortresses in Muscat record their presence. They commissioned the Danish botanist Carsten Niebuhr to write a description of the country. The red hair and some oddities of dialect of the Shihuh who inhabit parts of the southern coast are sometimes attributed to these incursions. Dutch, French, and British imperialists coveted control of Oman, and the last persuaded Omani rulers to cede the Kuria Muria Islands strategically placed between Suez and Bombay, in return for support against their nominal Ottoman overlords. Fortune seekers have been tempted to Omani waters by rumours of guano and ambergris, further indications of high productivity. Famous research ships have explored these waters, including the *Challenger* in 1839, the *John Murray* in 1933-34, and the *Discovery* in 1963.

Thabit Zahran (1) reported three fish mortalities which he attributed to red tides, one on the Salalah coast in August 1976 in which an estimated 7 to 10 thousand tons of *Sphyraena*, *Siganus*, *Leth-*

Fig. 1. Red water near Qalhat, Oman (22°49'N, 59°16'E) in March, 1993.

rius, and *Epinephelus* were killed, and two smaller events near Ras al Madraka in October 1976, and north of Muscat in February 1978. Red tides and fish mortalities are probably very common in this region. Brongersma-Sanders (2) recorded red tides here in September 1936 and October 1950, and linked them to the fish cemeteries discovered during the *John Murray Expedition*.

Accounts of "discoloured water" in this region, always of concern to navigators, are recorded in early editions of the *Gulf of Aden Pilot* (1st edition 1863). Such events are undoubtedly more common than these few episodes indicate. Mr.S.H.G.Bennett (pers.comm.), on behalf of Commander Mugaddam Bahry of the Oman Royal Navy, writes that their Hydrographic Department has been keeping records of red tides since 1991. He says "Red tides seem to occur

from February to March, principally from Ra's al Hadd (22°30'N, 59°48' E) to Ra's Abu Daud (23 19 N, 58 56 E) decreasing in intensity towards the NW." Colour photographs supplied to me by the Navy show stunning patches of discoloured water (Fig. 1). In Mr. Bennett's words, an event in March 1993 "was thick and orange ... and had been forced towards the coast by diurnal onshore winds", and another in March 1994 "was more jelly-like and a reddish brown colour". These were in 22°45'N, 59°18'E, and 22°45'N, 59°21'E respectively.

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Ed.

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NATO ADVANCED STUDY INSTITUTE
 Held jointly with SCOR and IOC
 “The Physiological Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms”
 Bermuda Biological Station
 27 May-6 June, 1996

Bermuda discussion groups:

Zooplankton grazing measurements

Measurements of particle ingestion are frequently reported in dinoflagellate blooms, with clearance rates often highly variable. Discussions focused on outlining routine procedures that should be employed in grazing experiments. Manipulation and handling of the grazer populations and prey were intensely discussed, from collection, concentration, acclimation, enclosure, duration and sampling procedures. Similar discussion was initiated for prey. Short discussions of several routinely used techniques were also made, including experiments using changes in prey concentration, labelled fluorescent prey, gut filling and the dilution technique. The group concluded that meticulous and careful handling of grazer and prey would eliminate many of the artifacts likely to lead to the high variability noted in the literature,

and that some techniques must be cautiously employed in blooms where initial prey densities might be below the detection limits of the procedure. To further lower variability in grazing measurements, future studies should use HAB species from the same geographic region as the grazers and, if possible, use natural communities at ambient concentrations in one of the treatments. Further, zooplankton abundance needs to be assessed in the field so that estimates of grazing pressure on blooms can be determined.

Kevin Sellner, Jeff Turner

Bulk-phase rheology and small-scale processes

Rheology is study of the deformation of materials, particularly those materials showing both viscosity, the mechanical

property characteristic of fluids, and elasticity that is characteristic of solids. Such materials include colloids, particularly polymers. In seawater, they increase the viscosity and provide elasticity. Measurements, recently made of this thickening, indicate that at certain scales, particularly in dense phytoplankton blooms and under conditions of little turbulence, such polymeric thickening dominates the viscosity contributed by the small molecules of water and salt. Then the polymeric component largely determines how whole seawater deforms and flows.

An apparatus for measuring water flow rate through fish gills as a function of hydrostatic pressure difference, from 5 cm to 0.1 cm water (approx. 500 to 10 Pa) was demonstrated. A similar apparatus had previously been used to show reduction in flow (increase in viscosity) produced by HAB species such as *Gymnodinium cf. nagasakiense*, and thereby

confirm a theory that even though flow is rapid between fish-gill lamellae, it can be significantly reduced by the increased viscosity produced by algal mucus. This reduction of gill ventilation may contribute to the death of fish and other organisms in blooms of some species of ichthyotoxic algae. The advantage of using a freshly killed fish as a rheometer is that it exactly duplicates the scales, geometry and perhaps gill-surface effects occurring in living fish during a HAB attack.

After the demonstration a discussion followed on rheology and small scale processes in relation to HAB ecophysiology, during which the following points were made.

State of the art

- i) Exceptionally, particularly during dense blooms, exopolymeric material produces observable mechanical changes to the water, such as apparently increased viscosity, oiliness, etc. Normally, however, any such changes are not obvious to the casual observer, except in surface slicks.
- ii) At relevant length-scales and at the mechanical deformation forces *in situ*, recent evidence suggests that the water that bathes particles, especially phytoplankton and bacterial cells, is frequently not an ideal (i.e., Newtonian) liquid. Colloidal, organic material imparts “excess” viscosity as well as elasticity to the intercellular continuum.
- iii) This exopolymeric matter comprises glycocalyxes, looser slime surrounding cells, organic aggregates, and more diffuse material. It acts as an adsorption medium for some substances, thereby reducing their molecular diffusion. By viscous and perhaps also elastic effects, it can reduce or even stop flow and thus also turbulent diffusion.
- iv) Over the last decade, classical rheological measurements (i.e., using mechanical spectra) on phytoplankton cultures and seawater have shown: a) a polymeric “excess” viscosity negatively related to shear rate, generally by a power law exponent; b) a polymeric elasticity. Under the conditions of measurement used for the most part, the elastic modulus is typically <20% of the “excess” viscous modulus, but the time scale considered and the amounts of shear

Tery Cuci (left) conducts flow cytometry demonstration.

- might change this; c) both “excess” viscosity and elasticity are positively related to chlorophyll content by a power-law exponent between 1.0 and 1.5; d) both “excess” viscosity and elasticity are approximately log-normally distributed.
- v) Somewhat analogous measurements of the rheological properties of material at the air/sea surface show that the material responsible for these properties (polymers consisting of polysaccharides with associated peptides/proteins and lipids) is largely similar to those responsible for the bulk-phase rheological properties. This material is often in exchange between the air/sea surface, no doubt other surfaces, and the bulk phase.
- vi) Some organisms are likely to have evolved to use exopolymeric secretions, sometimes along with differential solar heating in layers, to modify: a) dispersion dynamics for nutrients, toxins and allopathic substances; b) inter-organism recognition and control of adhesion. Such recognition and adhesion control is used in predation, and both parasitic and pathogenic infection. It is also used to avoid such predation and infection, and to manage both sexual and trophic encounters. The potential for such employment of polymers increases with population density.
- vii) When seawater passes through fish gills, plankton nets and filters, clogging is frequently correlated with

phytoplankton abundance. Filter-clogging, which can be produced either by hard particles (e.g., some cells) or by soft ones (e.g., organic aggregates), represents a potential low-tech method to measure polymeric viscosity at different shear stresses (hydrostatic pressure difference across a filter) and length scales (both filter pore size and flux per unit area of the filter). However it is still not known how to relate such clogging to the distributions of mechanical and adhesive properties in the seawater continuum.

Areas requiring more attention

- i) Three-dimensional flow trajectories of particles relative to each other in the sea, particularly at length scales from mm to dm, are largely unknown. These should be studied as a function of stratification and rheological properties.
- ii) Secretion of polymers by HAB phytoplankton and other species, should be investigated as a function of the abundance and the physiological state of the organisms concerned.
- iii) Future work should target the overall structure of dissolved/colloidal organic matter (including recently produced exopolymers) and of aggregates (including transparent exopolymeric particles). This requires characterisation in much more detail than hitherto.
- iv) Structure at the primary (make up

- of oligomers), secondary (oligomer arrangement in polymers), tertiary (polymer geometry, including folding and cross-links) and quaternary (aggregate structure and inter-aggregate bridging) levels should be determined at the same time as the foregoing points i) and ii).
- v) The mechanical constraints exerted by colloidal organic matter on ensembles of both sinking and swimming cells, and their effects on swimming, sinking and fluxes, should be determined at scales from mm to 1000s of km.
 - vi) There is a need to determine the relationships between contents of phytoplankton and dissolved/colloidal organic matter and clogging of filters, nets and gills by seawater over different length-scales (both mesh size and flow/unit area) and deformation pressures (cross-filter hydrostatic pressure differences).
 - vii) Physical oceanographers should be urged always to bear in mind that their studies concern a mixed polymeric/aquatic, inter-cellular continuum.

Different approaches

- i) Classical rheometry: determination of mechanical spectra using rotating (essentially viscosity only) or oscillating (viscosity and elasticity) Couette-system rheometry.
- ii) Fish-gill, net and filter clogging.
- iii) Molecular techniques, including fluorescence depolarisation.
- iv) Characterisation of primary to quaternary structure of dissolved/colloidal organic matter.

Proposals for future research

- i) Investigation of rheology (viscoelasticity) over different deformation regimes and length-scales (measuring gaps), both in HABs and in non-HAB water, as far as possible combined with other investigations (toxicity, nutrient and other physiological states of the algae, C:N ratios of the dissolved/colloidal organic matter and the algae, abundances of phytoplankton, bacteria and other organisms, flocculation and stickiness of phytoplankton and exopolymeric matter, characterisation of primary to quaternary structure in dissolved/colloidal material).
- ii) Development of low-tech methods

to measure polymeric viscosity at different deformation stresses, suited for ship-board use. Such methods must be calibrated against classical (i.e., hi-tech) rheometric methods.

- iii) Characterisation of turbulence in vitro and in situ as modified by various concentrations of HAB and non-HAB phytoplankton species and their mucus.
- iv) Investigation of the roles of viscoelasticity, flocculation, adhesion and surface forces, as functions of species make-up and density, on:
 - v) Vertical and lateral fluxes of: a) chemical elements; b) viable genetic materials.
 - vi) Toxic and allopathic action, by HAB and non-HAB species.
 - vii) Organism behavior.
 - viii) Alteration of predator-prey interactions in the plankton food web.

Although this section addresses marine environments specifically, it is likely to be broadly applicable also to bodies of fresh water.

Ian Jenkinson, Patrick Gentien

Advanced Imaging and Flow Cytometry

A brief review of advanced fluorescent cytometric techniques was presented with special reference to methods most applicable to eco-physiological studies of phytoplankton. All these approaches are amenable to rapid, automated, single-cell analysis by either flow or imaging cytometry.

Phylogenetic stains, including both antigen-antibody and oligonucleotide approaches, were discussed. These techniques allow the identification of species or specific groups of cells in mixed natural samples. Significant work is required to make these methods practical and easy.

Constitutive fluorescent probes were reviewed for algae. These are fluorochromes with affinities to specific cell constituents including the nucleus (nucleic acids), cell wall, membranes, mitochondria, dinoflagellate thecal plates, storage products, and vacuoles.

A third type of fluorescent technique that is potentially useful is the intracellular functional probe. These are fluorochromes that indicate processes or biochemical states within cells such as mitosis, pH, enzyme activity, free glu-

tathione or protein -SH groups, transmembrane potential, hydrogen peroxide, oxygen radical formation, or general oxidation state.

Discussion following this brief review focused on ideas of cellular constituents and processes that might be important to measure for understanding phytoplankton eco-physiology. Ideas proposed included total protein, membrane lipids, food vacuole presence or activity for mixotrophy, redox state of the quinone pool, toxin effects on membranes of potential target cells, and other life cycle indicators. It was not known by this group whether fluorescent indicators of many of these processes yet exist. Several members of the group were interested in attending an advanced workshop such as the one that has been held at Bigelow Laboratory on functional fluorescent probes for phytoplankton.

The next major topic of discussion was the use of imaging and flow cytometry for measurements of mixotrophy using fluorescently-labelled prey. Discrepancies between flow cytometric methods and microscope methods were reported. Possible explanations for this were discussed including detection by flow cytometry, overlapping of fluorescently-labelled prey with mixotroph cells in microscope preparations, and fixation artifacts. An experiment to test some of these hypotheses was done using the instruments at the workshop. Results (obtained after the Discussion group meeting) suggested that autofluorescence by *Chrysochromulina* in the green light emission band interfered with detection of ingested fluorescently-labelled prey using flow cytometry. This led to an underestimation of ingestion using flow cytometry relative to microscope methods.

The last topic discussed was the detection of rare events by flow and imaging cytometry. This issue is important in detecting harmful algal species in natural samples before they achieve bloom concentrations. Topics discussed included the number of cells statistically necessary to detect, the effect of flow rate on sample analysis time, and various methods of concentrating samples.

Mike Sieracki

Dinoflagellate cell cycle and cell regulatory mechanisms

During the NATO-ASI on HABs, a number of issues emerged that were addressed in part at the ecological level, but which would benefit from a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms regulating phytoplankton growth and behaviour. A fundamental question which remains unresolved for most HAB species is whether blooms result from events which "trigger" explosive growth rates of HAB species, or whether blooms result from the advection of cells and maintenance of dense populations by either physical or biological mechanisms. A group of approximately 20 ASI participants met to assess the current status of our knowledge of cellular mechanisms which regulate growth and cell division in dinoflagellates and to discuss how insight into cellular regulations can contribute to the understanding of bloom dynamics.

Two presentations provided focus for the discussion. The first, presented by Fran Van Dolah, provided recent evidence identifying the presence of a typical eukaryotic cell cycle regulatory machinery in dinoflagellates. The cell cycle in eukaryotes is regulated by two classes of proteins, the cyclins and cyclin dependent kinases, which together control progression of a cell into both DNA synthesis and cell division. The presence and mitotic activation of a cyclin dependent kinase in *Gambierdiscus toxicus*, as well as specific inhibition of cell cycle progression by inhibitors of cyclin dependent kinases, indicates that this dinoflagellate possesses at least some of the normal eukaryotic cell cycle machinery, and supports the notion that the eukaryotic cell cycle regulatory machinery was acquired quite early in evolution of eukaryotes.

Fran Van Dolah demonstrates neuroreceptor assay methods. Neuroreceptor Binding Assays, (See p. 18).

Gaspar Taroncher-Oldenburg next presented his recent findings on cell cycle dependent toxin biosynthesis. Working with synchronized cell populations, he found that production of saxitoxins by *Alexandrium fundyense* is restricted to the G1 phase of the cell cycle. Using the technique of differential display of mRNA, he has found a number of genes under transcriptional regulation, which are differentially expressed during different cell cycle stages. This is a significant finding in that many dinoflagellate proteins studied to date appear to be regulated at the translational level. It is anticipated that probing the differentially expressed genes may yield components of the saxitoxin biosynthetic pathways and/or cell cycle regulatory proteins.

The general conclusion of this discussion group was that understanding dinoflagellate growth regulation at the molecular level will help to elucidate the mechanisms involved in bloom initiation and progression. Furthermore, it will also allow the development of probes for determination of *in situ* growth rates or other cell cycle events which could prove useful in monitoring and predicting blooms.

*Fran van Dolah,
Gaspar Taroncher-Oldenburg*

NATO-ASI demonstration:

Demonstration on dinoflagellate mixotrophy and heterotrophy

A two-hour laboratory demonstration on methods for detecting and studying mixotrophy, phagotrophy, and parasitism in toxic and non-toxic dinoflagellates was

attended by approximately 70 NATO-ASI students. The demonstration was chaired by Dr. Edna Graneli (Lund Universitet, Sweden), with presentations by Drs. Per Juel Hansen (University of Copenhagen, Denmark), Catherine Legend and Per Carlsson (Lund Universitet) and Wayne Coats (Smithsonian

Institution). Dr. Hansen discussed feeding mechanisms and preferences of heterotrophic and mixotrophic species, and described methods for direct observation of phagocytosis. He also presented a 25-min video showing ingestion of prey by selected dinoflagellate taxa and documenting lethal and sublethal effects

of a toxic strain of *Alexandrium tamenon* on the algivorous ciliate *Favella ehrenbergii*. Drs. Legrand and Carlsson reported methods for determining ingestion of prey and dissolved/colloidal substrates using a variety of fluorescent tracers. Their demonstration included a 30-min video and a 20-min slide presentation that reviewed procedures for labeling potential prey (FLA and FLB), documented ingestion of phytoplankton by *Heterocapsa triquetra* and *Chrysochromulina polylepis*, showed uptake of fluorescently labeled dextran (200K m.w.) by *Alexandrium catenella*, and provided evidence of food vacuoles in *Dinophysis acuta* and *D. acuminata* using DAPI staining. Dr. Coats described cytological staining procedures and fluorescent techniques to reveal the presence of parasites and ingested prey inside photosynthetic and heterotrophic dinoflagellates. His 25-min slide/video presentation considered methods for estimating in situ feeding rates of mixotrophic dinoflagellates and described the development and impact of parasitic dinoflagellates (*Amoebophrya ceratii*) on several host species.

Optical Oceanography & Remote Sensing Demonstration

John Cullen reviewed the principles of optical oceanography, detailed the value of optical measurements in long term monitoring studies, research and aquaculture. He also demonstrated the a spectral radiometer buoy in the field and discussed its applications and versatility (Cullen et al. in press *Limnol. Oceanogr.*). Pat Tester reviewed the application and availability of sea surface temperature (AVHRR data from the NOAA COASTWATCH Program) and ocean color data sets (CZCS data files on line at <http://daac.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). CCOAST software designed for viewing NOAA SST files was distributed to workshop participants.

Molecular Probes

This demonstration had three elements. Chris Scholin demonstrated DNA probes for identifying Pseudo-nitzschia species, Jane Gallagher discussed the use of RAPD to differentiate closely related organisms, and Jose Cordova discussed antibody detection of algal species.

DNA Probes

Nucleic acid probes are cited as tools with great potential to speed the detection and quantification of HAB species. Realization of this goal, however, has been difficult for many reasons. Chief among these are a paucity of sequence data and corresponding lack of species-specific probes. Another significant and often overlooked challenge is to develop a probe application strategy that is simple, rapid, and does not demand specialized laboratory facilities and highly trained personnel to execute. In a step towards meeting these demands, whole cell and sandwich hybridization assays were devised for detecting a variety of toxic and nontoxic Pseudo-nitzschia species. In all cases the probes are targeted towards species-specific sequences of large subunit ribosomal RNA (rRNA).

Whole cell (in situ) hybridization begins with a chemical fixation to preserve macromolecular structure followed by an alcohol rinse to dehydrate the specimen and reduce autofluorescence. Fixed cells are subsequently exposed to a solution containing a fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide, rinsed to remove unbound probe, and finally viewed by epifluorescence microscopy. End products of this procedure are intact cells that contain fluorescent probes bound to complementary sequences of rRNA in the cytoplasm. Filter-based sample processing is used to collect cells from a known volume of water and to apply a series of labeling reagents sequentially. After requisite reactions are completed, filters are mounted on standard microscope slides to view and enumerate the labeled cells. This method requires about three hours to execute.

In contrast, sandwich hybridization begins by homogenizing a concentrated sample of living cells in a chaotropic solution that both liberates nucleic acids and protects them from degradation. Two separate hybridization reactions then ensue: capture of target rRNA sequences from the crude lysate using an oligonucleotide tethered to a solid support, and binding of an enzyme-tagged signal probe to a sequence near that of the capture site. Visualization of the captured rRNA/signal probe complex is accomplished enzymatically yielding a macroscopic, colorimetric product on a plastic "dipstick". The extent of color development can provide a measure of the abundance of target species in the original sample. By coupling this tech-

nique with existing instrumentation one can detect a variety of Pseudo-nitzschia species in less than 1 hr; approximately 15 min are required of the person performing the assay. Simultaneous detection of multiple species within the same sample is possible.

RAPD Analysis

RAPD's stand for random amplified polymorphic DNA. The technique is a variant of the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using single primers of 10 base pairs with random sequences. Wherever complimentary sites are located on opposite strands, amplification will occur. The amplification products are then visualized on gels.

Problems with replication of RAPD bands can be caused by impure DNA, small differences in concentrations of reactants in the amplification mixture, and variation among batches of chemicals provided by manufacturers. It was recommended that reactions be repeated more than once.

Empirical data show that the method is only effective as a phylogenetic tool for resolving relationships among very closely related groups, such as populations. It's main use for HAB organisms is for tracking individual genotypes and may be of utility for tracking introductions of organisms. RAPD bands specific to individual genotypes could be cloned and made into probes for very closely related organisms in natural populations.

Antibody Detection of HAB Species

Marine biologists and taxonomists responsible for monitoring programs around the world face every day with the challenge to maintain an accurate record of the organisms that cause algal blooms (red tide). This information is becoming a crucial factor to take the appropriate measures to mitigate the impact of red tide in our society. However, this objective is hampered and sometimes difficult to fulfill due to laborious analysis of field samples under the microscope, by the increasing number of organisms that cause HABs and by the limitation of the morphotaxonomy to distinguish them. A method that could efficiently respond to these problems is the generation of monoclonal antibodies (MAb).

The MAb application in research as well as in biomedicine is notorious due

to their accessibility and accuracy. Perhaps one of the most important properties of MAbs, is their ability to identify a specific antigen regardless of its distribution, localization and number within a complex mixture. An example of this unique feature is the distinction of lymphocytes subsets by specific identification of a membrane antigen.

In this laboratory demonstration the first MAbs generated to the Chilean strain of *Alexandrium catenella*, organism that produces PSP were presented. These MAbs primarily recognize antigens that are theca specific with a specific discrete distribution, suggesting a polarization of the theca. At present, evaluation of their species-specificity is underway. Also, they were coupled to different sized beads that are able to "precipitate" fixed *Alexandrium* cells, indicating their potential use to isolate them from a phytoplanktonic cells mixture. Preliminary attempts to use them in monitoring samples soon will be performed by employing magnetic beads.

MAbs for other *Alexandrium* species are reported. However, limited information is reported to overcome the problems encountered during the process that could help other researchers to generate MAbs for a different toxic species. Therefore, during this laboratory demonstration, special emphasis was made to discuss these problems and some alternatives were provided.

Jane Gallager

Summary of Flow and Imaging Cytometry Demonstrations

Three sessions for approximately 15-20 people each introduced the use of flow and imaging cytometry methods for plankton analysis. Imaging cytometry was demonstrated using a system with two different imagers: a cooled CCD, slow-scan camera used for picoplankton analysis, and a 3-chip color CCD with frame integration used for nanoplankton analysis. Principles of image analysis were introduced with special reference to analysis of fluorescing cells. Methods for automated image analysis of pico- and nano-plankton samples were demonstrated and methods for microplankton analysis were discussed. Examples of natural plankton samples from local Bermuda waters were used to demonstrate the methods.

The basic principles of flow cytometry were reviewed using a FACScan flow cytometer. This included sample flow rate, excitation light sources and beam size, hydrodynamic focusing of the sample stream, data display, and measured parameters. Demonstrated techniques included the analysis of groups of phytoplankton such as cyanobacteria, cryptophytes and *Prochlorococcus* from local Bermuda waters; analysis of mixotrophy in *Prymnesium* ingesting fluorescently labelled algae; and DNA analysis of live and dead cells of both cultures and natural assemblages using new fluorochromes.

One advanced session was held for more detailed discussions of particular problems and analysis of samples brought by participants. Samples included 1) *Alexandrium* stained with both an oligonucleotide, large subunit rRNA probe, and a cell surface immunological probe; 2) *Pseudonitzschia* stained with dual oligonucleotide probes; 3) comparison of *Gambierdiscus* and *Prorocentrum* cells stained with propidium iodide and a new DNA fluorochrome for cell cycle work.

Mike Sieracki and Terry Cucci

Neuroreceptor Binding Assays

The toxins of interest to researchers and regulatory agencies concerned with harmful algal bloom (HAB) events encompass a diverse array of structures, activities, and relative potencies. Attempts to develop reliable as well as efficient means of detecting and quantifying these compounds and their toxicity represent an ongoing effort in many laboratories throughout the world. The neuroreceptor binding assay approach to the selective detection and quantitative estimation of marine biotoxins, including the saxitoxins, brevetoxins, domoic acid, and ciguatoxin, is a promising technique anticipated to find application in both research and regulatory settings, and was among the Demonstration Sessions conducted at the NATO-ASI on the Physiological Ecology of Harmful Algal Blooms held at the Bermuda Biological Station for Research (27 May-6 June, 1996).

A total of about 50 ASI participants attended the receptor assay demonstrations, which were held over a period of four evenings. The primary aims of the

demonstration were to introduce participants to the basic principles and procedures of neuroreceptor binding assays, and to encourage members of the HAB scientific community to incorporate this method into research/regulatory activities requiring determination of sample toxicity. Participants were provided with detailed write-ups on individual assays, including background information, protocols, and technical/purchasing information for the necessary supplies and equipment. Each demonstration session consisted of an introductory lecture followed by the performance of assays in a laboratory setting. The lecture was used to outline the rationale for employing the receptor binding approach, discuss the theoretical basis of the assays, provide an overview of the protocols, and summarize the sample types with which the receptor assays are compatible. Participants were encouraged by the robust/rapid nature of these assays, especially their utility in diverse sample matrices (e.g., shellfish, algae, cyanobacteria, bacteria, and mammalian serum and urine) and the prospect of obtaining near-real time toxicity data associated with HABs.

In the laboratory, receptor assays for several toxins, including domoic acid, saxitoxin, and brevetoxin, were either demonstrated or discussed. Participants were shown the steps required to perform these straightforward, radioisotope-based assays, all of which are conducted in a 96-well microplate format. It was pointed out that the versatility of these assays permits results to be quantified on either a microplate scintillation counter or a conventional rack-type liquid scintillation counter, depending on the type of 96-well format used. Those assays demonstrated involved filtration of samples onto a 96-place filter mat into which a solid wax scintillant was melted prior to counting on a model 1450 Microbeta Trilux scintillation counter, kindly provided by Wallac, Inc. (Gaithersburg, MD) for the demonstration. Many participants commented on the obvious advantages of using the solid scintillant rather than conventional liquid scintillants. A highlight of the demonstration was the performance of the Microbeta scintillation counter which is capable of analyzing 96 samples in about 15 minutes, while the Windows-based controlling software shows a real-time display of the activity for individual samples. The laboratory part of the demonstration concluded with a discussion of what is required for data

processing and interpretation in order to obtain results of the highest possible quality.

By the end of the demonstrations, considerable interest in the neuro-receptor binding assays among the participants was apparent. Based on the nu-

merous requests for additional information and discussions of collaborative research projects involving these assays, this approach to assessing toxicity has the potential to become an integral tool in the study of HAB toxins and their effects.

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Conclusions and recommendations:

1. Mixotrophy by hab species

Justification:

It is now clear that many HAB species have the potential for mixotrophic nutrition. The ability to utilize both photosynthetic and heterotrophic pathways may give species of mixotrophic HAB a competitive advantage over strictly autotrophic members of the phytoplankton. Thus, we cannot understand bloom dynamics, the effects of eutrophication on plankton communities, or life cycle dynamics of key HAB taxa without thoroughly understanding the forces driving mixotrophy and the extent to which autotrophic processes are supplemented by heterotrophy.

Research Priorities:

- Develop reliable methods to detect and quantify mixotrophic nutrition
- Determine the mixotrophic potential of key HAB species
- Identify factors that induce or enhance phagotrophy in photosynthetic organisms
- Investigate the effects of natural and anthropogenic eutrophication on HAB mixotrophy
- Evaluate the effects of mixotrophic nutrition on toxicity of HAB species
- Assess the significance of mixotrophic HAB on the structure and function of marine food webs.

2. Thin layers and microphysics of the pycnocline

Justification:

Different strategies lead some species, amongst which a large proportion of the harmful species, to accumulate into thin layers (some tens of centimeters) associated with the pycnocline for long periods of time. Spatial scales in these fea-

tures have not yet been investigated but there is evidence that they can extend, at least, to the 10 km scale.

For different species, greater knowledge of behavioral responses responsible for such accumulations or confinement would allow better understanding of HAB dynamics. Detailed studies of a few target species might lay the basis for typifying functional groups of species. Such detailed studies would thus also provide insights into biomodification of the physico-chemical environment.

Although all the detailed processes leading to and maintaining these thin layers are not yet understood or even described, the displacement and maintenance of these layers are of paramount importance to the prediction of harmful events. The behavior of these boundary layers has not yet been sufficiently investigated by physicists (for example in cross-shelf and along-shore transport).

Recommendations:

Studies of the microphysics at the appropriate scales, involving physicists, should be encouraged in order to:

- Characterize the microphysics and chemistry at the viscous and intermediate sub-ranges in order to quantify the various processes influencing the development of HABs.
- Characterize the processes leading to the formation and the erosion of thin layers.
- Develop an understanding and modeling of mesoscale advection in thin layers in relation to cyclic forcing, weather events and biologically mediated reduction of turbulent viscosity (through turbulence suppression, e.g. by differential solar heating of phytoplankton layers, and/or by viscoelastic polymer secretion).
- In order to understand 3D-movements of these features, development of appropriate instruments is necessary (density-adjusting floats, fine-scale

profilers, particle analyzers, video systems, in situ rheometers).

3. Macronutrients

Justification:

There has been an increase in anthropogenic nutrient inputs to many coastal areas. Correlative evidence indicates that HABs have increased in response to elevated nutrient loading in localized regions (e.g., North Sea, Baltic Sea, Seto Inland Sea, Tolo Harbor). Some HABs have also been related to natural nutrient dynamics (e.g., upwellings) in coastal areas. The relationship between macronutrients and mechanisms of HAB formation/maintenance remain to be determined. In particular, it is unknown whether HAB species have unique nutrient utilization capabilities and strategies which allow them to out compete other species, or whether, in the presence of high nutrient availability, the occurrence of HABs is controlled by grazing pressure. Other unresolved issues include the role of nutrient supply ratios in selecting for HAB species, and the importance of DOM either directly, as a nutrient source, or as an indirect promoter of HABs.

Future research priorities:

- Determine the nutrient utilization capabilities and strategies of selected HAB species in comparison with co-occurring phytoplankton. Interactive field and laboratory studies are essential. Field studies may require the development of new technologies for focusing on individual species in conjunction with more traditional approaches.
- Determine how nutrient concentration, composition, ratios, and cycling influence the occurrence of HABs. Retrospective analysis of long-term data available in some regions or evidence preserved in cores can provide

information about the past occurrence of HAB in areas where nutrient inputs have increased. Process-oriented field studies of current HABs, especially recurrent, predictable HABs where all phases of the bloom dynamics can be studied, are essential.

- Evaluate the role of DOM as either a direct source of nutrients which HAB species can utilize or as an indirect stimulant of HABs through interaction with bacteria and the microbial loop.
- Investigate the relative importance of top-down control in regulating species composition of HABs.

4. Populatin genetics/ biogeograpny

Justification:

Morphological features and life histories are the primary criteria used to distinguish phytoplankton species. However, a single group of organisms defined in this way a species may include multiple genetic variants or strains. Definition of species and their associated infraspecific variants is critical for understanding the basis of biodiversity, toxin production, physiological optima and tolerances and origins of HABs on local and global scales. The presence of genetic variation even within populations of apparently unspecific blooms creates serious problems for studies based on clonal cultures because it is unclear how representative these cultures are of natural populations. There is an urgent need to expand the study of genetic variation in HAB species with particular reference to the roles of biogeography, genetic isolation and long-term changes in genetic diversity.

Research Priorities:

- Molecular tools are particularly useful for these studies. Currently available techniques are limited and progress is slow because of the small number of investigators in this area. More technology needs to be developed, particularly those techniques that bridge the critical gap between lab investigations and natural populations. More training opportunities need to be provided for phytoplankton ecologists to learn these tools.
- The requirement of morphotaxonomy to provide a platform for species identification and genetic comparisons necessitates a renewed effort in this area. The impending loss of expertise in

morphotaxonomy creates a need for training new people in traditional as well as advanced methods of recognition of morphospecies.

- Support for culture collections is declining. However, a primary requirement for the study of genetic variation among HAB organisms is the availability of multiple isolates of the same species from different geographic areas. Recognition of the importance of culture collections is required and more financial support is needed to maintain and expand them.
- Physiological studies should recognize the potential for variability for such parameters as environmental optima and tolerance ranges, quantity of toxins and toxin profiles because the patterns of variation may yield useful insights into the relative importance of adaptive factors controlling the distribution of organisms. More technology, such as automated counting methods, need to be developed that facilitates the examination of larger sample sizes.
- Multidisciplinary approaches to the study of genetic variation can yield critical insights. Support for multidisciplinary investigations that examine HAB species from both morphological and subcellular perspectives should be encouraged.
- There is provocative evidence that anthropogenic dispersal of HAB species has occurred. The introduction of harmful organisms may be accompanied by the introduction of harmful genes that may be incorporated into native populations. Further assessment of the extent of role of human-assisted dispersals and their occurrence in the past needs to be conducted.

5. Freshwater/ stratification

Justification:

Some degree of vertical stability is essential for the development of phytoplankton blooms. Such stability can be provided by density gradients caused by heat or by low salinity inputs. Examples of the latter include estuaries and buoyant coastal currents. However, freshwater input also brings with it a supply of poorly characterized, land-derived nutrients: macronutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorous from agricultural and industrial/domestic sources; micronutrients including metals and vitamins; and, dissolved and particulate organic materials. The latter may serve as growth

promoters (e.g. chelators) or directly as nutrients.

The linkage between HABs and freshwater input has been established in many areas (e.g. *Phaeocystis* blooms associated with Rhine River discharge, *Heterosigma* blooms in the Strait of Georgia, *Alexandrium* blooms in the southwestern Gulf of Maine coastal current, and *Pyrodinium* blooms along river plume fronts). Research is needed to understand the mechanisms underlying this linkage and to elucidate the relative importance of the many factors which may be operating.

Research priorities:

- determination of in situ algal species growth rates and physiological status within and outside areas of freshwater influence as they relate to the chemical constituents of the water;
- determination of the relative importance of physical effects and algal behavior vs. direct growth stimulation;
- elucidation of the mechanisms underlying blooms occurring within low salinity water masses vs. those occurring at the boundaries of water masses;
- develop an understanding of the influence of the timing of freshwater inputs and stratification to bloom dynamics

6. Small scale physics, behavior, and photosynthesis

Justification:

We have a conceptual model, often termed the Margalef mandala, that provides a framework for describing how physiology, behavior and hydrography interact to promote or maintain algal blooms. We also have good descriptions of algal blooms in several well-studied regions. However, we are not yet able to couple sufficiently detailed information on algal physiology and behavior into realistic hydrodynamic models to describe single species bloom events in natural water columns. Consequently, our present numerical models are not robust in the real world.

Research Priorities:

- Incorporate physics into all HAB initiatives to provide information on the environmental conditions that support bloom development, maintenance and decline.
- Develop effective methods to characterize how organisms behave under

the influence of variable environmental factors.

- Develop appropriate methods to characterize photosynthesis and nutrition under relevant, natural hydrodynamic variability. Conventional culture techniques are not sufficient.
- Improve coordination among physiological/behavioral characterizations, biological-physical modeling, and quantitative descriptions of hydrography and natural communities.

7. Ecophysiology of toxin production in hab species

Justification:

Toxic secondary metabolites are produced by several photosynthetic eukaryotic and photosynthetic/nonphotosynthetic prokaryotic groups of microorganisms. To date, research on these compounds has focused on structural elucidation, detection methods and mechanisms of action. The next major areas for understanding the physiological function of toxin production should be a rigorous investigation of their biosynthetic pathways and genetic regulation. Some data is available on these topics but we have only begun to really understand these processes.

The effect of environmental factors on production of phycotoxins has not been investigated in detail for any of the toxin groups but some information is available for a limited number of strains and key species, e.g. PSP, NSP, and DSP toxins in *Alexandrium* spp., *Pyrodinium bahamense*, *Gymnodinium catenatum*, *G. breve* *Prorocentrum* spp., anatoxin production in *Anabaena* spp., and domoic acid production in *Pseudonitzschia* spp. We know some information on saxitoxin and neosaxitoxin biosynthesis yet the biosynthetic pathway and its genetic regulation among the different toxin-producing organisms is unknown. In contrast, the structure and biosynthesis of domoic acid is better understood and we can now ask questions concerning its regulation and physiological importance. A total understanding of the function of these toxins will only be achieved when we understand their structure, biosynthesis, genetic regulation and ecophysiology. Emphasis should be on the functional roles of toxins in the primary source organisms e.g. do these toxins serve an intrinsic or an extrinsic function?

Research Priorities:

- Determine the kinetics of growth, toxin biosynthesis, and interconversions.
- Identify the cellular location of the toxins and the timing of their production in the cell cycle.
- Characterize the components of the toxin biosynthetic pathways.
- Determine if toxins are directly involved in predator-prey interactions.
- Determine if toxins serve an allelopathic function against other algae, bacteria or fungi, including the role of other compounds in stimulating or inhibiting the effect of the toxins.
- Determine the critical interactions between extrinsic environmental factors and the genome in regulating toxin biosynthesis, catabolism and sequestration (phenotypic vs. genotypic variation in HAB species).
- Model the production of toxins for extrapolation to natural populations.
- Determine the evolutionary origin of the toxin biosynthetic genes.
- Develop an international source for toxin standards and reference materials.

Understanding the genetic basis for toxin production will provide valuable insights into their ecophysiological role in bloom dynamics.

8. Bacterial-algal interactions in hab population dynamics, cellular growth, and toxicity

Justification:

Co-existing with algal communities containing HAB species are microbial assemblages which, like the algae, undergo changes in species composition, exhibit nutrient competition, and produce bio-active compounds, including toxins. These and other microbial processes are influenced by the algal community and, in turn, can potentially influence the population dynamics, cellular growth, and toxin characteristics of the algae. It is now clear that bacteria can produce both intracellular and extracellular compounds with algicidal as well as growth inhibiting or stimulating effects. Moreover, available evidence demonstrates that bacteria not only can modify the toxicity of algal cells, but can themselves synthesize certain 'algal' toxins.

Research Priorities:

We must now characterize natural bacterial assemblages associated with HABs, and establish whether production of growth/toxicity modifying substances and/or toxins occurs on temporal and spatial scales permitting them to influence algal bloom dynamics, cellular growth, and toxicity. It is also essential to determine whether bacteria constitute an important source of 'algal' toxins in the context of trophic transfer and seafood safety issues. Suggested approaches to achieve these objectives include:

1. Apply classical and molecular approaches to characterize the temporal/spatial association of bacterial assemblages with HABs, and define the systematic as well as functional relationships between bacteria and these algae.
2. Isolate and characterize bacterial and algal bio-active metabolites, and determine their respective effects on bacterial and algal growth and/or toxicity, including elucidation of the mechanisms involved and the patterns of synthesis in natural communities.
3. Evaluate the role of toxigenic bacteria as a point of entry for the transfer of 'algal' toxins between trophic compartments in aquatic food webs, and assess the contribution of these microbes to the toxification of fisheries resources.
4. Determine the distribution of toxin genes among bacteria and extrachromosomal elements (e.g., plasmids, viruses) as a means of explaining the phylogenetic diversity of organisms capable of synthesizing certain 'algal' toxins, and identifying potential mechanisms for the lateral transfer of these genes.

9. Trace Metals and Chelator Interactions

Trace metals including iron, manganese, cobalt and selenium have been hypothesized to limit the production of harmful algal blooms. Examples include limitation of *Alexandrium tamarense* (Gulf of Maine), *Aureococcus anophagefferens* (Peconic Bay), *Heterosigma* sp. (Osaka Bay) and *Chattonella antiqua* (Seto Inland Sea) by iron, the limitation of *Chrysochromulina* sp. (Kattegat) by cobalt and the inhibition of *A. tamarense*, and *C. antiqua* by copper. In most cases, the importance of a single trace met-

al was determined when the addition of that particular metal stimulated the growth of a HAB organism in culture.

In recent years, the importance of chemical speciation and organic complexation in the open ocean has revolutionized our view of how trace metal chemistry affects phytoplankton growth dynamics. Current data on trace metal concentrations in coastal waters, along with information on chemical speciation and biological interactions indicate that it is plausible that trace metals influence the growth and species composition of coastal phytoplankton communities. This new information on trace metal availability now needs to be applied to the development, density and frequency of harmful algal blooms.

Areas for future research include:

Obtain more detailed information on trace metal concentrations and speciation in coastal waters. Determine techniques to estimate their bioavailability to harmful algal bloom species.

- Examine the mechanisms of uptake.
- Examine the effects of multiple nutrient limitation.
- Determine the minimum cell quotas for trace metals.
- Examine the effects of trace metal limitation on cellular biochemistry including toxin biosynthesis.
- Examine the importance of bacteria trace metal interactions.

10. Life Cycles

Knowledge of life cycles and cell cycles is fundamental to the understanding of formation, maintenance, and decline of harmful algal blooms. The water column or benthic origins of bloom inocula, cell growth, bloom termination and long-term species are mediated by poorly understood or largely unknown life cycle events. Most HAB species have benthic phases, which are believed to be important in species survival and persistence, but control on interactions between planktonic and benthic phases remain to be elucidated. The following information on the basic biology of these organisms will be vital to furthering our understanding of bloom dynamics:

- full elucidation of life histories for all HAB species (including asexual and sexual reproduction);
- the development of rapid and reliable molecular/immunological probes for

detection of life cycle stages, leading to improved and/or automated recognition;

- description of cell cycle morphologies (for example, division stages) facilitating calculation of in situ growth rates;
- determination of endogenous cell cycles, for example, the gating of cell division on a diurnal basis and annual cycle of excystment;
- identification of the specific nutritional and environmental triggers as well as genetic controls involved in stage transformation, and the conditions required for successful transformation;
- determination of the survival and metabolic activity of benthic stages;
- understanding the physics of warm column – sediment transport and subsurface sediment mixing and burial in deep sediment and their influence on life history.

11. Emerging techniques and technology

Justification:

An understanding of HAB phenomena requires the detection of causative species and the toxins they may produce. Analogous problems exist in biomedical diagnostics, and many techniques and technologies used for those purposes are applicable to HAB research. For example flow cytometry, antibody and DNA probes, phycotoxin-specific receptor binding assays have been transferred and used successfully in the laboratory and, to varying degrees, in field studies.

The interfaces between traditional disciplines have often yielded scientific breakthroughs, thus interdisciplinary collaborations should be fostered to solve the difficult issues relevant to understanding HAB phenomena. Programs should be developed that foster cross-training and collaborations between biomedical and HAB researchers.

Research priorities:

Inexpensive, simple, efficient, and accessible methods for identification and detection of all HAB species and toxins must be developed. Methodologies and tools should be made widely available to the field as a whole as they are developed. Confirmation of the efficacy and utility of new techniques in the field requires multi-disciplinary investigations that could include: taxonomy, physical oceanography, ecology, and biochemistry.

- *Probes for species identification.* DNA and antibody probes have been developed and tested in the laboratory for a limited number of HAB species. These probes must now be tested in the field.
- *Toxin detection.* Receptor assays for toxins in HAB species have been demonstrated in the laboratory. These assays now need to be tested for utility in natural populations.
- *Measurement of in-situ growth rates.* Methods for determining in situ growth rates are needed in order to understand the mechanisms driving HABs. Flow and imaging cytometric

PHOTO: DR. SERGE MAESTRINI (CREMA, L'HOUMEAU, FRANCE).

“East meets West” at the Bermuda NATO ASI, Dr. Maija Balode (University of Latvia), and ASI Director Dr. D.M. Anderson (WHOI)

methods have been demonstrated to be useful in the field and show promise for HAB species.

- *Probes for physiological status.* Many fluorescent probes for measuring intracellular conditions have been developed for mammalian systems. Application of these tools to algal physiology may yield new understanding of the regulation of phytoplankton population dynamics.

Since the choice of reference taxa is critical due to potential genetic variability, culture repositories should be supported and expanded internationally.

Recommendations from Graduate Student Participants at the ASI

Reflecting upon the scientific interactions which brought about the formation of this NATO-ASI and the fruitful exchange of ideas which occurred throughout it, we would like to see the continuation of such cooperation on the following levels:

- Integrated Monitoring of HABs: monitoring of harmful algal system dynamics to include aspects such as the microbial loop and grazing measurements.
- Collaboration, to promote the integration of laboratory and field studies, to facilitate the cross-fertilization of scientific fields to further our understanding of HABs on a multidisciplinary level (i.e. physicists, chemists, limnologists), to develop an "international laboratory" to encourage the exchange of knowledge and technology, and to disseminate information regarding HABs to all levels of society
- Establishment of Graduate/Post-Doctoral fellowship programmes for the study of HABs

Now on WWW!

The IOC Directory of Scientists and Managers in Toxic and Harmful Algae and Their Effects on Fisheries and Public Health, is now available as a searchable data-base at

<http://www.unesco.org/ioc/isisdb/html/habd.htm>

HARMFUL AND TOXIC ALGAL BLOOMS

The IOC and the Laboratory of Bioorganic Chemistry, Tohoku University is happy to announce that the Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Toxic Phytoplankton, Sendai, Japan, 12-16 July 1995 are now available.

Through joint effort of the Organizing Committee, University of Tohoku and the IOC it has been made possible to publish the Proceedings at low cost. With the cooperation of Instituto Espanol de Oceanografia and Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution it has been made possible to ensure distribution also at a very low cost.

We can therefore offer you the Proceedings for 30 US\$ per copy. It can be ordered from the addresses below according to where in the world you live.

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Future events

IOC-ICI-IEO Training Course on Toxic Phytoplankton, Analytical Techniques for Marine Phycotoxins, Vigo, Spain, 29 June-16 July 1997. The IOC, the Institute for Iberoamerican Cooperation (ICI) and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) are organizing a course on toxic phytoplankton with special emphasis on the detection and quantification of marine phycotoxins (bioassays, in vivo and in vitro, chemical, immunoenzymatic and biochemical techniques). Lecturers will include staff from IEO, Laboratorio de Sanidad Exterior (European Community Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins), and Conselleria de Pesca, Marisqueo e Acuicultura (Xunta de Galicia), plus other guest lecturers from Spanish and foreign institutions. The Course will be given in Spanish and priority will be given to applicants from Latin America. Deadline for applications is 30 March 1997. Contact: IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Instituto Espanol De Oceanografia, Cabo Estay, Candio, Apartado 152, 36280 Vigo, Pontevedra, Spain, Fax.: +34 86 49 23 51, E-mail: insovigo@cesga.es

IOC Danida Training Course on the Taxonomy and Biology of Harmful Marine Microalgae, August 1997. This course will focus on identification and preparation techniques supplemented by lectures on different aspects of the biology of harmful algae. Teaching staff will include: Dr Yasuwo Fukuyo (Univ. of Tokyo), Prof. Øjvind Moestrup (Univ. of Copenhagen), Dr Jacob Larsen (Univ. of Copenhagen/IOC Centre), Organized by the University of Copenhagen, and IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen. For application forms, contact: the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Botanical Institute, Ø. Farimagsgade 2D, DK-1353 Copenhagen K, Denmark; fax: +45 33 13 44 47. Deadline 7. April 1997.

IOC-NorFA Nordic-Baltic Course on the Taxonomy and Biology of Harmful Microalgae, Tvärminne Zoological Station, Finland. 17-24 August 1997. The objective of the course is to improve the taxonomic skills of the participants in order to enable them to make reliable identification

of phytoplankton species causative of harmful algal events in the Baltic region. The Course will cover also ecology and toxin chemistry particularly of blue-green algae. A number of seats are available for participants from the Baltic countries and from Northwest Russia. Course lecturers will include: Dr. G. Cronberg, University of Lund, Dr. K. Kononen, Finnish Institute of Marine Research, Dr. J. Larsen, IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Professor Ø. Moestrup, University of Copenhagen, Denmark; Dr. K. Sivonen, Finnish Institute of Marine Research. Deadline for applications: 1 April 1997. Application form can be obtained from the address below and from the WWW at <http://www.unesco.org:80/ioc/oslr/oslr.htm>. Contact: IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen. (See below).

International Symposium on Marine Cyanobacteria and related Organisms. Institute de Océanographie, Paris, 24-28 November 1997. Organizers are ORSTOM, University of Sidney, CNRS, French Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The symposium will focus on new techniques such as molecular phylogeny and cell sorting. Contact: Dr. Loïc Charpy, ORSTOM, Centre d'Océanologie de Marseille, Rue de la Batterie des Lions, F-13007, Fax. (33) 491 01 16 35, E-mail: charpy@orstom.rio.net

Second International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety (ICMSS II), Iloilo City, Panay Island, the Philippines, 13-17 November 1997. A forum for scientists from various disciplines; and shellfish growers, processors and regulators. Discussions will focus on the latest research, commercial practices and standards concerning the contamination, purification and overall safety of molluscan shellfish with respect to chemical, biological and microbiological contaminants. Contact: Dr. Rhodora A. Corrales, Chairman, Organizing Committee, Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines, Diliman, Quezon City 1101, the Philippines; fax: (63-2) 9215967; E-mail: hod@msi.upd.edu.ph

IOC publications

- International Directory of Experts in Toxic and Harmful Algae and their Effects on Fisheries and Public Health. Published jointly with the US NOAA. *IOC INF Document 1015*.
- Design and Implementation of Some Harmful Algae Monitoring Systems. Co-published with ICES. *IOC Technical Series No. 44*.
- Summary Report of the Third Session of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms, Paris, 6-9 June 1995. Available in English, French, Spanish.
- Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), Volume 1, *IOC Manuals and Guides*, No. 31.

These publications are free of charge and available from the IOC Secretariat (Paris) and the IOC Science and Communication Centre, Copenhagen (see addresses elsewhere on this page).

- Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae, *IOC Manual and Guides No. 33*. The Manual is free of charge, but a fee of US\$ 30 will be charged to cover postage and handling. A cheque issued to H. Enevoldsen, IOC should accompany all orders. Excepted are marine science libraries and scientists in developing countries which can apply for delivery free of charge.

Literature for developing country libraries

Limited copies of the following titles are available from IOC's HAB Centre in Denmark, to libraries of marine science institutions in developing countries only:

- The Genus *Alexandrium* Halim (Dinoflagellata). **E. Balech, 1994**.
- Algae. An Introduction to Phycology. **C. van den Hoek et al., 1995**.
- Guide to Toxic and Potentially Toxic Marine Algae. **J. Larsen & Ø. Moestrup, 1989**.
- Proceedings of the Sixth International Con-

ference on Toxic Marine Phytoplankton.

- **P. Lassus et al. (eds.), 1995**.
- The Biology of Dinoflagellates. **F.J.R. Taylor (ed.), 1987**.
- Marine Phytoplankton. Identifying Marine Diatoms and Dinoflagellates. **C. Thomas et al. (eds.), 1996**.

Applications must be submitted and signed by the responsible librarian, and should indicate why the requested title is of specific interest to your institution and its ongoing research or

teaching. No requests from individuals will be honoured. Address applications to:

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HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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